

LEGISLATIVE REVIEW: CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 2019

TANGENTIAL TO ADMINISTRATIVE LAW

by

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ABSTRACT

The paper is legislative review supported by parliamentary debates. The purpose is to analyze the act through administrative law principles and debates.

First part gives a factual background of the statute and the key features of the act vis-à-vis the earlier act.

The second part gives a brief of the parliamentary debates before the passing of the act in the Lok Sabha. Although it is just a pointer type description of the criticisms pointed out during the debates but the substantial arguments are further dealt in the next part with the administrative underpinnings.

The following part tries to analyze the critical implementation problems which the act could face. The attempt is to interlink the text of the act to the administrative principles and give the positives and negatives of any unconscious omissions by the lawmakers. The purpose of this part is to acknowledge the advantages and requisites of the administrative principles for the effective and efficient law adherence and impact of the legislation by giving pros and cons of the sections. The same will be supported by any jurisprudence if any about the administrative issues. The similar provisions of any other statute lacking same administrative principles will also be touched upon by giving examples of already challenged provisions and the developments thereto. The larger impact would be to review the whole act through administrative lenses giving a more simplified and exemplified theoretical base glorifying the contemporary Indian Administrative law.

The last part will be inclusive of some measures which have been adopted either by the directions of the courts or as improvements after deliberations in other acts. It will be a summarized list of any effective amendments needed for abridging the loopholes in the current statute.

BACKGROUND OF THE BILL-

The act is CONSUMER PROTECTION ACT, 2019 No. 35 of 2019. It was introduced in the Lok Sabha on 8th July 2019 by Ram Vilas Paswan, the Minister of Consumer Affairs, Food and Public Distribution. The bill has replaced the Consumer Protection Act 1986. The debate of the Lok Sabha on the motion for the consideration of the Consumer Protection Bill 2019¹ has been a major source for analyzing the law in hand.

KEY FEATURES OF THE ACT-

- a. The consumer definition has been expanded as it now includes the people engaging in both online and offline transactions, teleshopping, multi-level marketing etc.². Hence not only the manufacturer but other intermediaries will also be liable under the act. However, the free services will not be covered under the act. Although this argument for free services was put by Shashi Tharoor but was unacceptable in the Lok Sabha when voted for.
- b. The central government has been authorized to ensure and regulate any unfair trade practices in E-commerce³, which has been defined as buying or selling of digital products through electronic market.⁴
- c. Unfair trade practices now include unfair, unilateral and unreasonable contracts also.⁵
- d. Definition of unfair trade practices has also been expanded.⁶

¹file:///C:/Users/lenovo/Documents/semester%206/consti/mid%20sem%20consti%20reading%20material/parliament%20debate.pdf

² section 2(7) of CPA 2019

³ Section 2(16) of CPA 2019

⁴ Sections 94 & 101(2)(zg) of CPA 2019

⁵ Section 2(6)(i) of CPA 2019

⁶ Vimal Chandra Grover v Bank of India, AIR SC 2181 (2000).

- e. Product liability can be claimed now through section 2 (35) which will let the consumer be compensated for any harm caused due to a defective product.⁷
- f. The central consumer protection authority has been formed as a new regulator through section 10 filling an institutional void in the regulatory regime.⁸ The investigating wing has also been formulated thereto.⁹ The district collectors also have powers.¹⁰ The body has to act according to the directions of the central government, therefore the authority of the executive body is restricted.
- g. Accountability has been ensured by penalizing any endorser when no due diligence exercised or any manufacturer for any misleading advertisements. The CCPA is empowered to impose penalties for the same.
- h. Due to the healthcare amendment and opposition from the medical fraternity, the deletion of healthcare from the definition of services has been done.¹¹
- i. There is an increase in the pecuniary limits of the different courts to ensure swifter disposal of cases.
- j. A mediation cell attached to each district, state and national commission will be set up to ensure fast resolutions.¹² The Consumer Disputes Resolution Commission will be set up.

PARLIAMENTARY DEBATES

- i. The debates starts with the discussion about how do we need the new bill. Followed by the provisions for product liability and the expansion of the definition of the consumer.
- ii. Our primary concern through the project is to look at the administrative body creation. The bill proposed to establish the CCPA for the protection, promotion and enforcement of the rights of the consumers and providing remedies through actions of recall, return and refund of products
- iii. Organizational structure of the CCPA
- iv. One of the points of discussion included the composition of CCPA.

⁷ Section 2 (34) of CPA 2019

⁸ Statement of Objects and Reasons of the Consumer Protection Bill, 2019.

⁹ Section 15 of CPA 2019.

¹⁰ Section 16 of CPA 2019

¹¹ Indian Medical Association v. VP Shantha & Ors. AIR 550 (1996).

¹² Section 74-81 of CPA 2019 (Chapter V)

- v. The query regarding the financial resources for the working of the authority in the state of Andhra Pradesh was raised.
- vi. The bill has disregarded the importance of the courts and eliminated the lawyers from the process. The easy way out is not to introduce an alternative disregarding the principal but to add an alternative complementing the problems of the principal act here that is protracted and complicated litigation.
- vii. The authority has been granted the power to consider the exceptions for the misleading advertisement policy but there is explicit list of the exceptions.
- viii. There is no mention of any PDS scheme or regulation of ration card for the majority of consumers who are poor in the nation and require such protection at the earliest and the most.

ANALYSIS OF THE ACT

A. HIERARCHY AND JURISDICTION

There is no mention of any hierarchy between the newly constituted body and the already existing consumer forums.

The CCPA has been empowered to enquire and investigate through a wing headed by the director general. It can even file complaints and intervene in matters. However the district collector has also been tasked to functionalize some inquiries. Therefore it has no clear mentions of the practical functioning of both the bodies. Since there is an overlap there are chances of high conflict of interests which the statute has not dealt with.

According to section 70 wherein the national commission has been authorized to lay administrative standards for all the state commissions but do not have authority to guide the CCPA from which also it has the jurisdiction to hear appeals from.

Moreover the factors over which national commission is supposed to hear appeal has not been mentioned and stays unclear, chances of a pandora's box to open.

B. POWERS AND INDEPENDENCE OF THE REGULATORS

Chapter III deals with the central consumer protection authority, for the regulation of matters relating to the violation of the rights of the consumers, unfair trade practices and contracts, misleading advertisements catering public interests.

The regulations made by the authority have to have previous approval of the central government and should not be inconsistent with the act. It can be for the procedure of engaging experts, procedure of the transactions of the business of the commissioners, powers and the procedures to be followed by the director general and any other matter deemed to be in need of.

C. DUTIES OF THE REGULATOR

There are no mentions of the duties of the regulator. Since it is an administrative body it must have duties and also more importantly when it recourses as a right guarantor for the consumers. Since there are no duties mentioned anywhere in the act it is imperative to put a proposal for the provision to check the power limitation and abuse of such power by the authority. Although there has been a provision for appeal to the national commission and thereafter the Supreme Court but there is no factors mentioned for invalidating the regulations of the authority. However it can be presumed that according to the ct the authority is not authorized to act against the objects or inconsistent with the act but there are no sanctions or penalties mentioned for the authority for the contravention of any such expectation.

D. COMPOSITION OF THE BODY

The chief commissioner and other such members for the central authority according to section 10(2) have to be appointed by the central government. The central government may also decide about the head office.

The regulations with the qualifications and appointment of members are all vested in the hands of the centre there are no empowerment provisions in the act itself.

According to section 11 the centre has the powers to make rules for the qualifications and method for appointments and recruitments. It may have the power to formulate and amend he terms and conditions of the commissioners and the chief commissioner of the central authority.

The earlier act has provisions for appointment of the central council commissioner and the state council commissioners by the chief justice of India and the chief justice or the respective High Courts respectively. Unfortunately there is no power to the judiciary but

the central government. There is no specifications for the required qualifications for the nominations or appointments and thereafter there is no way through which we can challenge the appointment with regards to the educational qualifications.

E. NO MECHANISM FOR THE QUALIFICATION OF THE TYPE OF CLAIM UNDER PRODUCT LIABILITY

F. DELEGATION OF POWERS

I. POWERS OF THE CENTRAL GOVERNMENT TO MAKE RULES

Section 101(1), the centre may make rules for any of the powers or provisions mentioned in the act

II. POWERS OF THE STATE GOVERNMENT TO MAKE RULES

Section 102 provides that although the power is with the state government but unless they specifically provide us with the rules the rules made by the central government will apply thereto.

III. POWER TO MAKE REGULATIONS BY THE NATIONAL COMMISSION

According to section 103 provides that only with the prior approval of the central government the commission may make rules with respect to any of the provisions of the act. It should be made only if necessary and expedient and should not be inconsistent with the act.

IV. POWER OF THE CENTRAL AUTHORITY TO MAKE REGULATIONS

G. ABUSE OF POWER BY THE CENTRAL GOVERNMENT

There are wide powers given the CG under section 18(2). Powers of CG for the conditions of the service of the members are left completely at the discretion of the CG. During the debates the Modi government is criticized for passing bills where there is too much of centralization of powers.

Only with the approval of the central government may these regulations be applicable.

From the powers granted by section 6(2)(c) the central government has encroached the powers of the state. However in the defense it was argued that the CCPA will have regional branches which imply no total centralization.

For such centralization of power the administrative law has to be anticipated for its well known principles. As such discretionary powers to make rules and regulations may affect the rights of the consumers, such powers can be controlled by bestowing of such discretion on the grounds of excessive delegation. However herein there are no means from the standalone reading of the act about the delegation of power to any authority. There is ambiguity as to what will be the procedure for formation of rules by the authorities under the act. Since there is no explicit provision for the delegation as such, we need to criticize the lawmakers for not recognizing the importance of delegation. Delegations will lead to efficiency, development, empowerment, leadership, improved and quick decision making and a better organizational structure. The act has very cleverly neglected the demise of the doctrine of non delegation as well.

H. AMBIGUITY FOR THE INCLUSION OF HEALTHCARE

I. CONSUMER DISPUTES REDRESSAL COMMISSION

Chapter IV lays down the provisions for CDRC.

The Consumer Disputes Redressal Commission will be set up at all levels as a quasi-judicial body. As according to section 70 it is also empowered with administrative control. There is no provision for a mandatory judicial member, which is a requisite for any quasi judicial body. There is unlimited power to the executive. In the erstwhile act the composition of the redressal commission included a person who was eligible to be appointed as a district judge. However it can be pointed out that in the earlier act it was a statutory body but herein it is a quasi judicial body. Still there remains the question of power to the executive and the judiciary being a violation of the separation of powers doctrine therefore being in violation of the basic structure of the constitution and therefore should be challenged under judicial review.

J. MEDIATION

During the process of mediation which is newly introduced one argued that there are chances of corruption. However chapter V has clearly laid down procedures to be followed for the appointment and composition of the panel of mediation. It has clearly laid down the duties of the mediators for disclosures, replacement of the mediators, preparation of the settlement report, etc. Therefore there are least chances of corruption

as such. However there may be colorable exercise of power wherein the mediating authority may confer an ostensible power which in reality has not been conferred on it. Moreover when such exercise is found the act is found to be invalid. There are no provisions for the sanctions of the mediation authority when such exercise of power is proved by the parties. However it can't be a ground for judicial review for abuse of power, as in the case¹³ it was held that this principle can be used alongside the mala fide discretion principle which is already a recognized ground for quashing an administrative action. There are provisions in the acts for an appeal against the mediation resolution but there are no certain factors for its implementation mentioned. We need to consider the pre existing recognized grounds for judicial review for such acts.

Moreover if the authority does not exercise the procedures properly then the whole decision will be invalid.¹⁴ The consequence of the non compliance when the non compliance cannot be waived¹⁵ is a judicial task to decide the validity of the decision and to impose further charges on the administering mediation panel.

Further section 78 also refers to the replacement of the mediator in certain cases but there is no clarity although it is mentioned that after satisfaction through information and proper hearing of the mediator. It is convincing as for an officer under this chapter, the principles of natural justice are obligated to be followed.

K. POWER TO IMPOSE PENALTIES

The central authority under section 21(7), will impose liability for misleading advertisements after considering the populations, frequency, vulnerability and the revenue from the offense. Herein we need to acknowledge the administrative principle of proportionality, developed in Europe, ensures that the administrative actions should never be more drastic relatively to the desired result. The test is to check the reasonability of the act. The doctrine is applied when there is an imposition of the quantum of punishment, courts do not follow the strict scrutiny but follow this principle to ensure no arbitrariness. Since the act has provided the parameters to be considered for the imposition of penalty the judicial review has been more easier for the application of the principle.

¹³ Somawanti v. State of Punjab.

¹⁴ R v Clarke 1 WLR 338 (2008).

¹⁵ R v Immigration Appeal Tribunal ex p Jeyanthan 1 WLR 354 (2001)

According to section 93 even the director general will be penalized through fine or imprisonment if they exercise search or seizure without acknowledging the absence of a reasonable ground for doing so. We need to discuss the liability of the government or state which can be contractual or tortuous and here the latter is at force. Herein the onus of proof is on the person alleging the administrative action to be mala fide. The constitution through article 300 has also authenticated such penalties. Jurisprudentially it was also held in a case¹⁶ that the officer will be liable for the damages of his negligent acts and on the same lines as an ordinary officer would be liable. The act has further followed the principle laid down in a case¹⁷ that when the public servant through oppressive or capricious acts has discharged his official duty causing injustice to a common man, although the state will be instrumentally liable for the payment of damages through public funds but thereafter may recover the amount as compensation herein the penalty from the public servant concerned.

The protection for all the officers from any penalty or proceeding has been made under section 98 only when act in good faith, done in pursuance of the act and according to the rules made therein under. The state has been vicariously held liable when the duty has been exercised bona fide and intra vires the powers of the officer.

CONCLUSION

Following are the concluding observations justifying the administrative review of the consumer protection act 2019-

- A. There is no clear delegation of powers with respect to the hierarchy and jurisdiction of the authorities empowered under the act that is the CCPA and CDRC.
- B. The power of the regulator CCPA is although not excessively delegated but have been excessively controlled which might curtail the independence of the regulator.
- C. Although there is an appeal against the regulatory authority but since there is no explicit mention of the duties, the adherence and sanctions to non adherence may be very

¹⁶ P. and O. Steam Navigation v. Secretary of State for India (5 Bom HCR App 1).

¹⁷ Lucknow Development Authority v. M.K. Gupta, 1 SCC 245 (1994)

subjective in case of non application of the procedures and the abuse of power conferred under the act.

- D. There is no mentions of the qualifications and terms of service for the people constituting the authority and all is left at the discretion of the central government which implies that the act still needs legislature that is the parliament to work upon it. In my opinion the legislature has escaped this legislating duty through putting provisions for further rules and regulations. Else it would have been contended in the parliament during the passing of the bill. The ambiguity was challenged but certainly not given much of an importance and relied on the efficiency of the central government that is the legislature to start encroaching upon the executive functions.
- E. There is no clarity upon the type of claims to be entertained for product liability and no mention of which authority is supposed to provide such clarity.
- F. For all delegation of power the central government has to be referred which may either lead to lesser transparency and accountability.
- G. The exercise of non delegation of power doctrine has been done. There are no provisions for ensuring accountability of the central government, which may lead to abuse of power.
- H. There is ambiguity about the inclusion of healthcare under the definition of services under the act. Ambiguity in the text may itself lead to inefficient functioning of the authorities empowered under the act.
- I. CDRC although being a quasi judicial body have full executive control as all executive members appointed by the legislature sidelining the judiciary altogether which may be violative of the separation of powers and therefore it requires a judicial review.
- J. There can be non exercise of procedures and colorable exercise of powers during the newly introduced mediation process. However there is no implies acknowledgment of such possibilities are there no sanction on the officers under the mediation except for the replacement of the mediator.
- K. Principle of proportionality and the acknowledgment of liability of the officers has been duly mentioned in the act.